

Method of Covert Chemical Marking of Sacred Artworks under the Threat of War: AURORA Project Trials in Ukraine

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Abstract— This study reports field testing of covert chemical marking for authentic artworks and movable objects of sacred use during expeditions to three sites of wooden sacred architecture in Ukraine. It examines the identification and protection of movable cultural heritage at risk from the armed aggression against Ukraine through the use of innovative chemical markers. The aim was to evaluate the adhesion and readability of the luminescent stealth marker Yellow INK across common substrates (wood, metal, stone, and textile) under field conditions. Markings were applied to 25 authentic objects using a reversible protocol that included an isolating acrylic layer to ensure removability, and luminescence was assessed under 365 nm UV radiation. The clearest luminescence and strongest adhesion occurred on porous substrates, particularly unfinished wood, plaster, and stone. Reduced durability was associated with hydrophobic surfaces and inadequate mixing of the marker composition. No adverse effects on object materials were observed during the trial when the isolating layer was used. The study presents one of the first large-scale Ukrainian field trials of chemical marking within the AURORA project and refines an application protocol for historically degraded materials, offering practical recommendations for preventive marking to support later identification and counter illicit trafficking.

Index Terms— cultural heritage, artworks, sacred art, covert chemical marking, luminescence, AURORA-EUPROJECT, monument protection, armed conflict.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE current geopolitical climate and the escalation of armed conflict in Europe, particularly the Russian Federation's full-scale invasion of Ukraine, have intensified the challenge of both physically protecting cultural heritage and ensuring its reliable legal identification. UNESCO and the Ministry of Culture and Strategic Communications of Ukraine report that hundreds of cultural heritage assets, including architectural monuments and historical and artistic sites, have been damaged or destroyed. Wooden churches and the movable sacred objects they contain are especially exposed because they are often located outside major protective infrastructures and are made of vulnerable organic materials.

Movable sacred heritage faces three interconnected risks. First, it is subject to direct destruction from shelling, fires, and bombardment, with wooden structures being highly susceptible to rapid loss. Second, occupation conditions and disorderly

evacuation increase the likelihood of illegal appropriation and looting, particularly of icons, liturgical utensils, and processional items. Third, illicit trafficking is enabled by weak documentation practices in small parishes, where the absence of consistent inventories and object marking can prevent timely entry into international databases and hinder detection at borders, facilitating circulation through foreign markets.

Traditional inventory and marking practices used in Ukrainian museum work are poorly suited to emergency conditions. Visible inventory numbers applied with paint or mechanical methods can be detected and intentionally removed, undermining later restitution. Such interventions may also be ethically and aesthetically unacceptable for sacred objects that remain in active liturgical use. In addition, full documentation according to national standards is labor-intensive and often impracticable during rapid-response operations, particularly when evacuation is imminent.

International frameworks, including the 1954 Hague Convention and its Second Protocol, stress the importance of preventive measures both before and during armed conflict, and these measures depend on reliable identification systems. Covert chemical marking offers a practical alternative by enabling rapid verification under portable UV illumination while remaining invisible in normal lighting. Compared with overt marks, it reduces the risk of deliberate detection and removal, can be designed to interact with surface microstructure or an isolating layer, and can be linked to digital registers through unique codes to support provenance verification and standardized accounting. On this basis, there is a clear need to modernize protective documentation for movable heritage in risk zones. The present study evaluates a field-applicable protocol for applying reversible luminescent markers to heterogeneous and naturally degraded sacred objects in Ukraine.

II. MOTIVATION

Current technological progress supports a reassessment of cultural heritage protection that integrates chemical, physical, and digital methods into a single operational framework. The AURORA-EUPROJECT addresses contemporary risks by proposing a multivector identification system that links

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material-level authentication to a virtual infrastructure based on blockchain. Within this alliance, and with the participation of Lviv Polytechnic National University, the Ukrainian component is oriented toward building an ecosystem capable of tracking artworks from the moment of creation or inventory through potential cross-border movement. The concept is grounded in three interdependent elements: material identification through the application of unique chemical marker formulations; digitization through blockchain, where each marker instance is associated with an immutable decentralized record that constrains provenance falsification; and miniaturized reading technologies, including portable UV scanners and microdetectors, that enable rapid verification by customs officials, museum personnel, and law enforcement.

The Ukrainian field study emphasizes practical adaptation under conflict conditions, where unstable electricity supply and the absence of laboratory infrastructure limit the feasibility of complex analytical procedures. In this context, the identification method must remain reliable while being simple to apply, interpret, and document. Research on cultural property marking in criminology and art history has long emphasized registration systems based on written records and photographic documentation, including guidelines disseminated by ICOM. However, experiences from recent conflicts in Syria, Iraq, and Libya have demonstrated that photographic documentation alone is often inadequate for restitution, because traffickers can modify an object's appearance through restoration, repainting, partial disassembly, or deliberate falsification, thereby weakening visual comparability and complicating expert attribution.

Several alternative technologies have been proposed to overcome these limitations. RFID tags are useful for internal accounting and storage management, but they are vulnerable to physical removal and may be masked by shielding, while the tag's structure can be detected visually or through inspection. DNA-based markers that encode unique identifiers in synthetic sequences offer high specificity, but verification typically requires polymerase chain reaction analysis, which is not compatible with rapid decision-making at border checkpoints. Micro-etching using laser technologies can provide durable identifiers on some metal surfaces, yet it may be unsuitable or destructive for fragile organic substrates such as wood, gesso, and painted layers, where mechanical or thermal stress can compromise original material.

Against this background, the selection of the luminescent chemical marker Yellow INK for field testing in Ukraine was based on its operational balance between resistance to forgery, procedural simplicity, and straightforward readability. Its use relies on fluorophores activated under 365 nm UV radiation, producing luminescence that enables verification without altering the object's visual appearance in normal lighting. At the same time, the intervention must comply with conservation ethics. A central conservation requirement is reversibility, ensuring that any applied materials can be removed without harm to the original substrate. In this study, reversibility is supported through the application of an isolating acrylic varnish

layer prior to marking, which prevents direct contact between the marker and the authentic material and allows controlled removal if necessary. This approach is consistent with the DOBA principles of documentation, justification, safety, and authenticity, which require that protective measures preserve historical integrity while remaining accountable and minimally invasive.

Accordingly, the present research tests the AURORA framework on complex, mixed, and naturally degraded surfaces typical of Ukrainian icons and church furnishings stored in wooden churches with unstable temperature and humidity regimes. By moving beyond controlled museum conditions, the study evaluates whether chemical stealth marking can remain legible, reversible, and materially safe in real environments shaped by conflict-related constraints.

III. EXPERIMENTAL METHODOLOGY: EXPEDITION RESEARCH AND TECHNICAL PARAMETERS OF MARKING

A. Geographical scope

Field research was carried out from May to June 2025 across three regions of Ukraine, selected to represent a broad geographic and typological range of traditional wooden sacred architecture (Figure 1). The expeditions covered sites in Vinnytsia, Khmelnytskyi, and Ternopil regions, allowing the protocol to be tested under different local conservation conditions, patterns of building use, and microclimates.

Figure 1. Map of Ukraine indicating expedition sites visited in 2025: (1) Vinnytsia region, (2) Khmelnytskyi region, (3) Ternopil region.

The study was organized in three field stages corresponding to the three sites (Fig. 2). Stage 1 focused on a wooden church representing architectural traditions associated with Podillia, the Dniro region, and Slobozhanshchyna. Eight authentic objects were selected to capture common movable heritage categories and material types, including nineteenth-century icons painted on linden panels and metal liturgical utensils. The objects presented typical preservation problems found in parish environments, notably surface soiling and traces of earlier non-professional interventions. These conditions were treated not as confounding factors but as a realistic test environment for assessing marker adhesion and readability on contaminated or

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uneven surfaces.

Stage 2 expanded the material spectrum by marking eight additional objects characterized by mixed construction and heterogeneous surfaces. The sample included wood with imitation gilding, textile components (wool), cardboard elements, stone, and fragments of interior decorative finishes. This stage was designed to evaluate performance where substrate absorbency, surface coatings, and fiber structure vary substantially within and between objects, which is common for church furnishings and composite devotional items.

Stage 3 was conducted in a church with the legal status of a national architectural monument, where conservation risks and procedural constraints are typically higher. Nine objects were marked, with priority given to altar elements and processional crosses because these categories are both highly valued and frequently targeted in theft. The materials included oil painting on wooden supports and lacquered wood. Many surfaces exhibited lacquer degradation and fine craquelure, increasing the risk that any liquid application could penetrate unstable layers or accentuate existing defects. For this reason, the application of the isolating layer was performed with heightened caution and continuous visual control. Across all stages, the sampling strategy produced a total set of 25 authentic items, providing comparative coverage of porous and non-porous substrates as well as stable and deteriorated surface conditions.

Figure 2. Three stages of the experimental case study

B. Physicochemical properties of Yellow INK and reading conditions

Yellow INK is a luminescent stealth marker formulated with fluorophores that absorb in the near-ultraviolet range. The reported absorption maxima fall between 255 and 365 nm, which enables excitation by common UV sources used outside laboratory settings. Upon irradiation, electrons are promoted to an excited state and subsequently relax to the ground state, emitting visible radiation perceived as yellow light. In this study, the emission was treated as a practical indicator of mark detectability rather than a spectroscopically quantified parameter, with the expected visible output lying in the approximate range of 560 to 580 nm. This emission range is advantageous for field verification because it can provide clear contrast against many historic substrates that show bluish fluorescence or brightening under UV illumination.

Marker readability depends strongly on illumination conditions. A wavelength of 365 nm was selected as the

standard excitation source because it is widely available in portable UV lamps and typically produces less distracting background blue emission than shorter UV wavelengths, improving visual discrimination of yellow luminescence, including on light-toned surfaces. For consistent field assessment, observations were performed with controlled lamp distance and viewing angle, with ambient lighting reduced where feasible to limit glare and reflections from varnished or metallic surfaces. The approach prioritizes rapid, repeatable verification that can be performed on site with minimal equipment, while still producing a sufficiently stable visual signal for documentation.

From an application standpoint, Yellow INK exhibits low viscosity suitable for brush-based deposition, which supports both precise placement and penetration into porous microstructures. At the same time, polymer additives are intended to reduce uncontrolled spreading on smooth substrates such as metal and lacquered wood by increasing cohesion of the liquid film and moderating flow. In practice, this balance is critical because excessive spreading can reduce code legibility and complicate later interpretation, whereas excessive viscosity can lead to uneven deposits and weak adhesion on rough or contaminated surfaces. The viscosity profile therefore functions as a compromise between capillary uptake on porous materials and controlled wetting on low-absorbency, hydrophobic, or coated surfaces. The whole process is summarized in Figure 3.

Figure 3. The features of ink application and reading conditions.

C. Marking protocol

The field protocol was designed to be conservative in material impact, reproducible under expedition conditions, and compatible with later professional conservation treatment. It follows a sequence of surface preparation, creation of an isolating barrier to support reversibility, controlled marker application, and standardized verification and documentation (Figure 4).

Before any liquid application, loose dust and particulate deposits were removed using a wide, soft brush to minimize abrasion and prevent particulate inclusion in the varnish film. Where superficial contamination persisted on hard substrates such as wood, plaster, or stone, a latex eraser was used to reduce the contaminant layer without introducing moisture. This step is critical because greasy or waxy deposits can increase surface hydrophobicity, leading to beading, poor wetting, and

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discontinuous films, which in turn undermine both adhesion and legibility of the isolating layer and the marker.

A thin layer of satin acrylic varnish was applied with a synthetic brush to form a continuous barrier between the authentic surface and the marker. The barrier serves two functions. First, it supports reversibility because the marker can be removed together with the varnish by a conservator using an appropriate solvent system, thereby limiting direct interaction with original paint, ground layers, or historic coatings. Second, it provides a more uniform and predictable interface when the original surface is highly heterogeneous, degraded, or locally friable. The varnish layer was applied sparingly to avoid pooling and to reduce the risk of penetrating unstable microcracks or lifting fragile surface layers.

After full drying of the varnish, the test symbols “Aa” were applied as a standardized micro-inscription. The use of microtubes allowed controlled dosing, supported repeatable line thickness, and reduced the likelihood of accidental spills, which is a non-trivial risk in confined interiors and on complex church furnishings. The inscription format was intentionally simple, enabling comparison of line continuity, edge definition, and fluorescence clarity across different substrates while limiting intervention area.

Figure 4. The schematic representation of the marking process.

Verification was performed with a portable UV lamp emitting at 365 nm. Whenever possible, inspection occurred in a darkened area of the site; where this was impractical, a shading screen was used to limit ambient light and glare. Each marked object was photographed using a scale and tripod to standardize framing and focus, producing a “marking card” suitable for later reference, comparison, and potential law-enforcement or customs use. This documentation step was treated as part of the marking process rather than an optional supplement, because an unrecorded mark has limited operational value during recovery or restitution.

A synthetic brush (No. 1) was selected for inscription because it allows thin, controlled lines that are difficult to detect in visible light yet remain readable under UV. Tool cleanliness was treated as a procedural requirement, as residual varnish, pigment, or earlier marker deposits can alter viscosity, weaken fluorescence, or produce misleading luminescent traces. Distilled water was used for rinsing, and separate brushes were reserved for varnish and ink to prevent cross-contamination. Basic personal protective equipment, including gloves and protective glasses, was used to reduce skin contact with chemicals and limit exposure to UV radiation during repeated inspections.

IV. RESULTS

Field testing of chemical marking in the context of Ukrainian wooden sacred architecture produced a structured dataset describing the interaction between Yellow INK and a range of historical substrates under real field constraints. For each of the 25 marked items, a standardized “marking card” was completed (Figure 5). The card captured the substrate type, surface condition, the presence of coatings or contamination, and a subjective assessment of luminescence brightness and symbol readability under 365 nm UV illumination.

Figure 5. Example of a “marking card”.

To support comparative interpretation, the objects were grouped according to (i) substrate porosity and capillary behavior, (ii) dominant material class (organic, mineral, metal), and (iii) the presence and character of surface coatings, including historic varnishes and modern synthetic finishes. Table 1 synthesizes the results derived from the individual cards.

Across the sample, four operational factors emerged as decisive for marking success: substrate porosity, surface hydrophobicity, the presence of micro-defects such as craquelure, and the completeness of reagent mixing.

Porosity and capillary effect

Objects with open porous structures showed the most stable and readable luminescence. Unfinished linden wood (for example, cards No. 1 and No. 23) and mineral substrates such as plaster (card No. 24) produced continuous, high-contrast luminescence (Figure 6).

Figure 6. Example of good luminescence: (a–b) linden substrate, (c) plaster substrate.

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The likely mechanism is capillary uptake of the marker or its carrier into the upper substrate zone, which reduces sensitivity to superficial abrasion and helps maintain line continuity. Under UV inspection, these marks appeared as uninterrupted strokes without optical breaks, supporting quick recognition of the “Aa” symbol.

TABLE I. COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF YELLOW INK LUMINESCENCE ON DIFFERENT SUBSTRATES.

Card No.	Substrate material	Subjective luminescence assessment
1	Linden wood	good
23	Linden wood	good
2	Linden wood painted with oil paint	acceptable
4	Linden wood painted with oil paint	acceptable
5	Linden wood, soiled and varnished	poor
6	Wood varnished with synthetic varnish	good
14	Wood varnished with synthetic varnish	poor
18	Wood varnished with synthetic varnish	acceptable
9	Wood covered with imitation material and synthetic varnish	good
20	Varnished painting surface	good
21	Varnished painting surface	poor
25	Wood painted with oil paints	good
10	Cardboard	acceptable
11	Cardboard	acceptable
13	Cardboard	acceptable
19	Paper	acceptable
3	Varnished brass	good
7	Varnished copper	good
12	Varnished brass	poor
17	Brass	good
22	Nickel-plated metal surface	good
15	Limestone	good
24	Plaster	good
8	Data not recorded	Data not recorded
16	Woolen textile surface	acceptable

Hydrophobicity and ink beading

Performance decreased markedly on smooth or hydrophobic surfaces, especially where the surface carried greasy deposits or low-energy coatings. On the soiled and varnished icon surface (card No. 5) and an altar element with a varnished finish (card No. 21), the ink tended to contract into

droplets rather than forming a continuous line. This beading behavior is consistent with limited wetting caused by wax residues, oily contamination, or certain synthetic varnish systems that reduce surface energy. As a result, the luminescent signal became fragmented, and symbol readability declined because the strokes broke into discrete points rather than continuous letterforms. Operationally, such fragmentation increases the probability of misreading, particularly when inspections are conducted quickly or under suboptimal lighting.

Craquelure and micro-defects

A noteworthy finding was the role of surface micro-defects in improving fixation on coated substrates. On a varnished surface exhibiting fine craquelure (card No. 20), the mark showed strong readability and apparent stability (Figure 7). Microscopic cracks likely acted as micro-reservoirs that captured the liquid phase, creating additional mechanical anchoring once dry. From a security perspective, this effect is potentially beneficial because pigment located within microcracks is harder to remove by superficial wiping than pigment deposited only on a smooth varnish film. This observation should be treated cautiously, because any intervention on a cracked varnish can also increase risks of penetration and staining if not controlled; however, under the isolating-layer protocol used here, the outcome was favorable.

Figure 7. Luminescence of “Aa” on a varnished substrate with micro-damage (card No. 20).

Mixing completeness and pigment concentration

Variability in brightness was also linked to procedural issues rather than substrate alone. During marking of sample No. 14 and several cardboard items, reduced luminescence was associated with settling of the luminescent filler within the microtube. This indicates that the reagent behaves as a suspension with a tendency to sediment over time, leading to inconsistent pigment concentration at the point of application. On this basis, the protocol should explicitly require active mixing at regular intervals during work, for example by shaking the microtube every 10 to 15 minutes, and more frequently if the working environment is cold or if marking is interrupted.

Reversibility and compatibility with conservation varnishes

The acrylic isolating layer performed its primary conservation function by acting as an intermediate membrane between the marker and the historic surface. Control observations indicated that the barrier limited diffusion of

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marker components into original paint and ground layers, supporting both ethical acceptability and the legal defensibility of the intervention. In practical terms, the marking can be framed as a temporary security measure that can be removed by a conservator once immediate risks decrease, without requiring aggressive mechanical action on the authentic surface.

Textile case: marking a woolen woven object (card No. 16)

The woolen textile object presented distinct challenges related to fiber structure and surface geometry. The pile and weave made it difficult to draw a sharply defined symbol using a No. 1 brush, and the mark tended to spread by absorption along fibers, producing softer edges than on hard substrates. At the same time, this diffuse absorption generated a volumetric luminescent effect. Under 365 nm UV radiation, impregnated fibers produced a visible halo that enabled rapid recognition of the marked zone, including from distances up to approximately 2 m (Figure 8). For field verification, this “halo” effect may be advantageous, as it supports quick detection even when fine line legibility is reduced. However, the trade-off is lower precision of the encoded symbol, which may matter if complex alphanumeric codes are introduced in future applications.

Figure 8. Luminescent surface of a woolen woven object (card No. 16).

V. CONCLUSION

The AURORA-EUPROJECT field trial conducted at monuments of wooden sacred architecture in Ukraine indicates that covert chemical marking can function as a practical identification and protection measure under wartime constraints. Yellow INK produced readable luminescence and operationally acceptable adhesion across a wide set of historic materials, including wood, metals, mineral substrates, paper-based supports, and textiles. This breadth is important for church collections, where objects are often mixed-material and unevenly preserved, and where the protective method must work without careful pre-selection of ideal surfaces.

From a conservation standpoint, the use of an acrylic isolating layer provides a defensible approach because it supports reversibility and reduces direct interaction between the marker and original materials. This increases the ethical and legal acceptability of the method for objects of high significance, including those still used in religious practice. In operational terms, the marker’s invisibility in normal lighting is a central advantage. It reduces the likelihood of rapid detection and removal and allows verification only when UV equipment is available. The protocol also proved compatible with expedition conditions, as it does not depend on laboratory instrumentation or uninterrupted electricity, which is critical for remote sites and for work conducted during humanitarian disruption.

Beyond the immediate technical findings, the Ukrainian experience within the AURORA alliance points to a structural requirement: chemically applied identifiers have limited value if they are not linked to a trusted, searchable record. A national register of chemically marked heritage, integrated with a blockchain-based platform, would convert individual marks into actionable evidence for customs, border services, and investigative bodies. If scaled, the approach could strengthen provenance verification, support restitution and legal proceedings related to illicit export, and extend protective documentation to small religious communities and private holdings that are typically outside formal state accounting.

APPENDIX

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